

PRINCIPAL REASONS FOR STUDYING LATIN

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Abstract. *The article discusses such semantic concepts as integration and the study of the Latin language. The article is recommended for pharma students. Universities can also be used for teaching Latin in universities.*

Keywords: *integration, Latin language, interdisciplinary connections, theory and teaching methods.*

Introduction: The Latin language belongs to the Indo-European family of languages, which includes the Baltic, Germanic, Slavic, Romance and other groups of languages. Latin was originally spoken by a small tribe of Latins who inhabited the central part of the Apennine Peninsula, the region of Latium, located along the lower reaches of the Tiber River. It was Latium - according to ancient Roman legend - that received Aeneas, who fled from Troy captured by the Greeks, and his distant descendant Romulus was destined to become the founder and first king of Rome. And it was Rome, at first just the capital of Latium, that, thanks to its expansionist policy, first took possession of all of Italy, and then the Mediterranean basin and became the capital of the vast Roman Empire. With the expansion of the geographical and cultural boundaries of the Latin language, its influence on the languages and cultures of the conquered peoples increased; it contributed to the unification of the empire and, as a result, became the language of intercultural communication of the Roman state.

The history of the Latin literary language and Roman literature is usually divided into three periods associated with periods of development of the socio-political life of Rome:

preclassical (III-II centuries BC),

classical (1st century BC),

post-classical (I-V centuries AD), the period of late Latin.

1. The pre-classical period is represented by the first monuments of Latin writing, the oldest of which date back to the 7th century BC. These include inscriptions of a ritual nature on a gold clasp and a silver vessel found in 1871 in the city of Praeneste near Rome. The most famous Roman written monument is an inscription on a piece of black stone found in 1899 during excavations of the Roman Forum. This inscription on a stone stele, containing a sacred formula (oath or spell), is written in archaic letters, very similar in style to Greek letters. Of extreme importance is the monument Law of the XII Tables - the first written monument of Roman law. The number of written monuments increases significantly, starting from the 3rd century. BC. This is due to the growing power of Rome, which united all of Italy and Greece under its rule. However, in Greece, a country with a highly developed culture, the language of the conquerors was forced to give way to the language of the vanquished: Greek became the second language of the Roman Empire. The long period of coexistence of the Latin and Greek languages, close contacts of the Romans with Greek culture and science enriched the Latin language, which borrowed a huge number of Greek words, expressions, and grammatical forms. The famous Roman poet wrote about this period: "Graecia capta ferum victorem cepit" - "Captive Greece captured the wild

conqueror.” The influence of Greek literature on Roman literature began to be revealed at the end of the 3rd and beginning of the 2nd centuries. BC. At this time, the first Roman writer, the captive Greek Livius Andronicus, translated Homer's *Odyssey* into Latin. Latin authors of this period created their works based on Greek models on subjects from ancient Greek mythology. The largest representatives of the archaic period in the field of literary language are Naevius, Plautus, Ennius, Cato the Elder and others.

2. The period of classical Latin. The literature of the classical period is represented by a brilliant galaxy of authors. In oratorical prose - Marcus Tullius; in historical prose - Gaius Julius Caesar, Gaius Sallust Crispus, Titus Livius; The most famous poets of this period are Titus Lucretius Carus, Gaius Valerius Catullus, Publius Virgil Maro, Quintus Horace Flaccus, Publius Ovid Naso. Thanks to the last three poets, whose creativity flourished during the reign of Augustus, as well as other talented poets of this time (Tibullus, Propertius), the era of Augustus was called the golden age of Roman poetry. The period of formation and flourishing of the classical Latin language was associated with the transformation of Rome into the largest slave-holding state in the Mediterranean, which subjugated vast territories in the west and southeast of Europe, northern Africa and Asia Minor. Latin dominated the territories of its own expansion, absorbing dialectal features, unifying and assimilating them, becoming the language of the Roman Empire. With the expansion of the geographical and cultural boundaries of the Latin language, its influence on the languages and cultures of the conquered peoples increased; it contributed to the unification of the empire and, as a result, became the language of intercultural communication of the Roman state.

3. The period of post-classical Latin. The most famous authors of this period: philosopher and poet-playwright Lucius Annaeus Seneca; satirical poets Marcus Valery Martial and Decimus Junius Juvenal; Roman historian Gaius Cornelius Tacitus; famous philosopher and writer Apuleius. The language of these writers is distinguished by significant originality in the choice of stylistic means, but the grammatical norms of classical Latin are almost not violated. Therefore, the division into the classical and post-classical periods has more literary than linguistic significance.

4. Late Latin period - the language of the late Western Roman Empire and the period of its fall. Ancient traditions in the literary work of this time, with rare exceptions, are fading away. The works of Ammianus Marcellinus and the Roman emperors remain significant as a historical source. A significant factor in the spiritual life of the period of the late empire was the spread of Christianity and the appearance of Christian literature in Latin by religious figures Jerome, Augustine, and others. In the works of late Latin authors, many morphological and syntactic phenomena already found their place, preparing the transition to new Romance languages. In the 5th century AD, after numerous raids by barbarian tribes from the north, the Roman Empire fell, Rome was conquered and destroyed, and new nations and states began to form in the place of the former Roman provinces. The Latin language becomes the basis on which national languages develop.

The complex process of interaction between vulgar (colloquial) Latin and the languages of conquered peoples led to the gradual formation of qualitatively new languages, which are now called Romance languages. The Romance (from the Latin *romanus* - Roman) group includes: the Italian language, functioning on the territory of the Apennine Peninsula, French and Provençal languages, which developed in the former Gaul, Spanish and Portuguese - on the Iberian Peninsula, Romansh - on the territory of the Roman colony of Raetia (in part present-day Switzerland and

northeastern Italy), Romanian - in the territory of the Roman province of Dacia (present-day Romania), Moldavian and some others, of which the Sardinian language should be especially noted as the closest to classical Latin of all modern Romance languages. Despite the common origin of the Romance languages, there are structural coincidences and divergences between them, due to a number of historical and sociolinguistic factors.

The fate of the classical Latin language, the language of the educated elite of Roman society, the purity of which was artificially maintained by Roman schools, was peculiar. In the era of the heyday of feudalism, when national states had not yet been formed and national languages had not become stronger, the Latin language acted in the West as a literary language. Medieval Latin spread widely as the language of literature, science, and international relations. During the Renaissance, humanist writers attempted to revive the language of Caesar and Cicero. The best representatives of this New Latin literature achieved great perfection in imitation of ancient models. But classical Latin was so far from the general ideological and cultural life of modern society that it could not serve it as a living spoken language. That is why, already in the Renaissance, the Latin language begins to give way to the national languages of the new Europe. However, until the 18th century. Latin retained its international significance, being the language of science and business correspondence.

It was taught in schools and universities in all Western countries. Only with the growth of national states did the strengthened national languages supplant the Latin language from all areas of science and culture. Currently, in the modern educational space there are trends towards the revival of classical education; the Latin language is an integral part of modern university education. The importance of the Latin language in the modern world According to the existing classification, the Latin language is classified as a “dead language”, since for more than a thousand years it has not been a means of communication for a certain ethnic group. However, is this really so? This question can be answered in the words of the famous Polish poet Julian Tuwim: “What kind of dead language is this if, without fading, it has survived millennia?...” In what form has Latin “survived” millennia, in what form continues to exist today? First of all, “Latin, “dying” for a thousand years, fertilized most European languages,” becoming the basis language for new national languages - Romance languages. Currently, more than 60 countries use Romance languages as national or official languages. The total number of speakers of Romance languages exceeds 600 million people.

The Latin language had a significant influence on the formation of the lexical vocabulary of many modern non-Romance languages, in which a large group of universally used words are Latinisms (borrowings from Latin). The role of the Latin language as a derivational (from Latin derivatio - branch) base of European languages is well known. For example, scientists have found that of the 20,000 most common words in the English language, about 10,400 are of Latin origin, about 2,200 are of Greek and only 5,400 are of Anglo-Saxon origin. And also, the teacher must have a pragmatic approach to the use of information and computer technologies, while in comparison with other means, the computer is a more modern tool for him. The use of computer educational programs in the process of language learning does not interfere with the solution of a communicative task, but, on the contrary, increases its effectiveness. Thus, from the above we can conclude that: – Information communication technologies are an additional method and direction in teaching languages, as well as Latin:

–Computer networks serve as a bridge for intercultural communication.

–Variability and integration of communicative orientation serve as a motivated leap for students into learning new things in Latin lessons.

–ICT is one of the effective ways to realize the creative potential of students and teachers.

In Russian studies there are still no calculations that would become a quantitative characteristic for vocabulary of Latin origin in the vocabulary of the Russian language, since there are direct and indirect Latin borrowings in the Russian language. Many of them are no longer perceived as words of foreign origin: school, institute, university, rector, director, student, lecture, audience, laboratory, vacation, session, colloquium and many others. Familiarity with Latin vocabulary, which forms the basis of the international dictionary of European peoples, broadens the linguistic horizons and contributes to a more accurate assessment of linguistic material, and allows one to correctly explain the spelling of words borrowed from Western languages. Mastering the grammatical system of the Latin language contributes to an understanding of general linguistic phenomena characteristic of Indo-European languages, a deep understanding of the Russian language, and improved literacy in both oral and written speech.

Conclusion: In the modern world, when multilingualism is becoming not only the norm, but also a necessity, knowledge of the Latin language becomes the basis for mastering many modern foreign languages. Many common literary Latin words, primarily those that have an abstract meaning, have moved into special spheres, and often function as part of not one, but different terminological systems. The Latin language is a kind of cultural code, since knowledge of it makes it possible to understand the meaning of philosophical categories, norms of Roman law, texts of the Christian religion, scientific (medical, economic, etc.) and political treatises. Latin is alive and in demand today, since through the means of this ancient language continuity, transmission and exchange of cultural information and cultural values are carried out throughout the world.

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